

Theoretical Investigation on Monomer and Dimers of Inhibitor of Cytochrome P450 Enzymes: 1-Aminobenzotriazole

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Abstract:

In this research, structures and properties of monomer and two dimers (1 and 2) of inhibitor of cytochrome P450 enzymes, 1-Aminobenzotriazole (ABT) have been studied by using functional hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The very good correlations observed between theoretical and experimental ^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR, FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra suggest that C-H \cdots N interactions of dimeric species should be expected in the solid phase, as was observed in the experimental crystalline structure of a quinolin benzotriazole derivative. NBO and AIM calculations suggest that dimer 2 with inverted positions of its monomers could be present in the solid phase because it evidence higher stabilities in both media. On the other hand, frontier orbitals studies support a higher reactivity of dimer 2 of ABT higher than the monomer and dimer 1, for which, the presence of dimer 2 containing N-NH₂ groups in ABT could justify the biological activities observed for this species with gap values between 4.5933 and 4.8164 eV different from

antiviral agents containing the C-NH₂ moiety, as amantadine and chloroquine whose gap values are around 4.3012-4.1116 eV. Finally, the presence of bands of monomer and of both dimers are predicted in the vibrational spectra and, hence, its completes assignments have been performed. The scaled force constants for the three studied species are also reported.

Keywords: 1-Aminobenzotriazole, molecular structure, harmonic force fields, vibrational analysis, DFT calculations.

Introduction

1-Aminobenzotriazole (ABT) has been used from long time as an inhibitor of cytochrome P450 enzymes (Colby et al., 1995; Mugford et al., 1992; Emoto et al., 2003; Balani et al., 2004; Sun et al., 2011; Parrish et al., 2015; Watanabe et al., 2016; Shaik et al., 2017; Sun et al., 2020; Sodhi & Halladay, 2021), as reported by Ortiz de Montellano (2018). Few experimental and theoretical studies related only to two fused benzyls and triazole rings were found in the

literature, however, combined crystalline structures obtained of benzotriazole rings with other rings or species have been recently published (Li et al., 2020; Karrouchi et al., 2023). N-H \cdots O, O-H \cdots N, and C-H \cdots F hydrogen bonds interactions were determined in the crystal of 1H-benzotriazole and tetrafluoroterephthalic acid (Li et al., 2020) while three different C-H \cdots N, O-H \cdots N and C-H \cdots O hydrogen bonds in the 5-((1H-benzo[d][1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)methyl)quinolin-8-ol (DD2) derivative were found (Karrouchi et al.,

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2023). Obviously, in ABT these types of interactions also are expected due to the presence of similar groups, as in DD2 where these interactions were observed between two N atoms of triazole ring of one monomer with two H atoms of benzyl ring of other monomer (Karrouchi et al., 2023). Thus, dimers species should be structurally considered in these derivatives because the interactions have influence on the properties, reactivities and biological activities. All these antecedents evidence that the studies related to structures and properties of 1-Aminobenzotriazole are important not only to understand the mechanisms and sites of action of this important inhibitor of cytochrome P450 enzymes but also, to know reactivities and behaviour of ABT in different media and, in addition, to identify this species in different environments. Thus, the aims of this work are: (i) to optimize monomer and two possible dimers of ABT in gas phase and water by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations, (ii) to predict their properties, reactivities and behaviours in both environments (Becke, 1988; Yang & Parr, 1988; Miertus et al., 1981; Tomasi & Persico, 1994; Marenich et al., 2009), (iii) to perform the complete vibrational assignments of monomer and dimers of ABT using the harmonic force fields, normal coordinates analyses and transferable scaling factors (Pulay et al., 1983; Rauhut & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002) and, finally (iv) to compute the scaled force constants of those species of ABT. Comparisons of experimental ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR, infrared and Raman of ABT with the corresponding predicted by calculations have confirmed the presence of monomer and both dimers of ABT (Online Spectral Database, N/A).

Material and methods

Structures of monomer and two possible dimers of ABT have been modelled with the *GaussView* program (Nielsen & Holder, 2008) while its optimizations in gas phase and water were performed with the Gaussian 09 program (Frisch et al., 2009). The optimized structures of monomer of ABT is shown in Figure 1. Here,

two dimers were proposed because in one of them (dimer 1) the monomers are in the same positions while in the other one both monomers are in inverted positions (dimer 2), according to published article of DD2 (Karrouchi et al., 2023). The optimized structures of both dimers of ABT can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 1. Structures of Monomer of 1 Amino-Benzotriazole (ABT) with Definitions of Rings and Atoms Labelling

Figure 2. Structures of Dimers of 1 Amino-Benzotriazole (ABT) with Definitions of rings and atoms labelling. Intramolecular H-Bonds are Represented with Dashed Lines

In all calculations, the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method was employed because this method generates better correlations to perform the complete vibrational analyses (Becke, 1988;) (Yang & Parr, 1988). Changes of volume of both species in the different media were predicted with the Moldraw program (Ugliengo, 1998). To investigate both species in water and to compute the solvation energies, the IEF-PCM and universal solvation method (SMD) were used (Miertus et al., 1981; Tomasi & Persico, 1994; Marenich et al., 2009). Atomic charges, topological and structural properties were calculated with the NBO 5.1 and AIM 2000 programs (Glendening et al. 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König et al., 2001). Merz-Kollman (MK) charges were computed to calculate the molecular electrostatic potentials (MEP) while with the *GaussView* program were graphed the mapped MEP surfaces (Nielsen & Holder, 2008; Bredas, 2014). Reactivities and behaviours of monomer and dimer of ABT were estimated employing the frontier orbitals and the chemical potential, electronegativity, global hardness, global softness and global electrophilicity index descriptors (Karrouchi et al., 2023; Parr & Pearson, 1983; Parr et al., 1999). Vibrational assignments for monomer and dimers were performed at the same level of theory with the harmonic force fields (Pulay et al., 1983; Rauhut

& Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Here, the normal internal coordinates of both triazole and benzyl rings were taken from reported work of DD2 (Karrouchi et al., 2023). In the dimers, only changes in the inter-monomers coordinates are observed. In these analyses, potential energy distribution (PED) contributions $\geq 10\%$ were considered. The Raman spectra predicted in activities for monomer and the two dimers were transformed to intensities (Keresztury et al., 1993). The ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of both species in aqueous solution were predicted with the GIAO method (Ditchfield, 1974). Finally, the electronic spectra for those species of ABT in aqueous solution were predicted using the Gaussian 09 program (Frisch et al., 2009).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations of Monomer and Dimers

First, in Figures 1 and 2 the optimized structures of monomer and both proposed dimers of ABT are presented, respectively while the calculated total and corrected by ZPVE energies, dipole moments and volumes of both species of ABT in the different media by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculated Total (E) and Corrected by ZPVE Energies (E_{ZPVE}), Dipole Moments (μ) and Volumes (V) of Monomer and Dimer of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory. Permittivity's (ϵ) and Differences of Energy (ΔG) Values are Also Included**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method							
MONOMER							
Medium	E (Hartrees)	E_{ZPVE}	$\mu(\text{D})$	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	ϵ	$\Delta G(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$	$\Delta G_{\text{ZPVE}}(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$
Gas	-451.3120	-451.1898	3.16	137.2	0		
Water	-451.3280	-451.2059	4.59	137.6	78.36	-41.97	-42.23
DIMER 1							
Medium	E (Hartrees)	E_{ZPVE}	$\mu(\text{D})$	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	ϵ	$\Delta G(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$	$\Delta G_{\text{ZPVE}}(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$
Gas	-902.6270	-902.3819	7.07	278.0	0		
Water	-902.6562	-902.4113	8.74	287.6	78.36	-76.59	-77.11
DIMER 2							
Medium	E (Hartrees)	E_{ZPVE}	$\mu(\text{D})$	$V(\text{\AA}^3)$	ϵ	$\Delta G(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$	$\Delta G_{\text{ZPVE}}(\text{kJ}/\text{Mol})$
Gas	-902.6270	-902.3819	7.15	283.1	0		
Water	-902.6563	-902.4113	8.83	288.4	78.36	-76.85	-77.11

In the table the permittivity's and differences of energy (ΔG) values are included. Analysing the results, the E values of all species have most negative values than the E_{ZPVE} and the dipole moment values are higher in solution, as expected because the acceptors (N) and donor's groups (N-H) of H bonds are possibly hydrated in solution. Clear expansions of volumes are observed in solution for the three species. Note that E dimer 1 is the same than dimer 2 in both media but higher volume expansion presents the dimer 1 while higher dipole moment value is observed in the dimer 2. The energy (ΔG) values correspond to the differences of E in solution – E gas phase while ΔG_{ZPVE} is the differences between E_{ZPVE} in solution – E_{ZPVE} gas phase. Note that ΔG_{ZPVE} have higher values than the corresponding to ΔG . The E values are corrected by zero-point vibrational energies (ZPVE) because the molecules present movements even in the zero K. Regarding the positions and orientations of dipole moment vectors of three species from Figures S1 to S3 (supporting material) we observed that in the monomer the magnitude of vector change few in solution while in this medium the vectors of both dimers change in significant form of magnitude and position but few changes in the

directions and orientations are observed. Hence, the both dimeric species of ABT justify the higher volumes variations in solution ($9.6/5.3 \text{ \AA}^3$), as compared with the change observed in the monomer in this medium (0.4 \AA^3).

Solvation Energies

In the above section, we observed that both monomer and dimers species of ABT are hydrated in aqueous solution due to the presence of donors (N-H) and acceptors (N) groups of H bonds which produce not only changes in the structures but also in volumes and, as a consequence different magnitudes and directions of the dipole moments vectors are observed. Hence, the solvation energies should be investigated in the two species in order to evaluate the different degrees of hydration of these species. Thus, from the difference between the corrected solvation energies by ZPVE ($\Delta G_{un}^{\#}$) and by the non-electrostatic terms (ΔG_{ne}) it is possible to calculate the corrected solvation energies (ΔG_c). Table 2 shows the corrected solvation energies by ZPVE and by the total non-electrostatic terms of monomer and dimers species of ABT in aqueous solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

Table 2. Corrected Solvation Energies ($\Delta G_{C/ZPVE}$) and Uncorrected by ZPVE Energies (ΔG_{un}) and Volumes Variations (ΔV) of Monomer and Dimer of ABT in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method. Units Expressed in kJ/mol**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method					
MONOMER ^a					
Medium	ΔG_{un}	ΔG_{ne}	ΔG_c	$\Delta V(\text{\AA}^3)$	$\Delta G_{C/ZPVE}$
Water	-41.97	9.97	-51.94	0.4	
	-42.23	9.97		0.4	-52.20
DIMER 1 ^a					
Water	-76.59	19.52	-96.11	9.6	
	-77.11	19.52		9.6	-96.63
DIMER 2 ^a					
Water	-76.85	19.60	-96.45	5.3	
	-77.11	19.60		5.3	-96.71
Oseltamivir ^b					
Water	-89.71	37.66	-127.37	-3.1	
Amantadine ^c					
Water	-15.21	7.86	-23.07	0.1	

Rimantadine ^d					
Water	-10.75	12.03	-22.78	0.2	

Note: ^aThis work, ^bVakili et al., (2021), ^cBrandán, (2021), ^dIramain et al., (2022)

Hence, for the monomer $\Delta G_c = -51.94$ kJ/mol is calculated as, $\Delta G_c = (\Delta G_{un}^\#) - (\Delta G_{ne}) = -41.97 - 9.97 = -51.94$ kJ/mol. For the dimer 1, $\Delta G_c = -96.11$ kJ/mol and $\Delta G_{C/ZPVE} = -96.63$ kJ/mol. Here, the dimer 2 presents a higher value ($\Delta G = -76.85$ kJ/mol). When these corrected values for ABT are compared with the ΔG_c values corresponding to antiviral agents, such as oseltamivir (-127.37 kJ/mol) (Vakili et al., 2021), amantadine or adamantadine (-23.07 kJ/mol) (Brandán, 2021) and rimantadine (-22.78 kJ/mol) (Iramain et al., 2022), where these two latter species are as free base, the values are very different from oseltamivir. Obviously, the different structures explain such differences (See Figure S4). In the three compared structures the donor common NH_2 group are bonded to C as C- NH_2 while in ABT the same donor group is bonded to N as N- NH_2 . Besides, oseltamivir has other donor N-H group and other acceptors groups (O) in addition to N atoms and, for these reasons, a higher value in the solvation energy is expected in this antiviral species, as compared to amantadine and rimantadine. Probably, the higher value observed for ABT than amantadine and rimantadine is justified due to N atom bonded to NH_2 group because it has a lone pair that could be hydrated in solution. This way, a different biological property as inhibitor of cytochrome P450 enzymes in ABT is expected.

Structural Study

So far, the experimental structure of ABT was not reported yet and, taking into account that correlations between theoretical and experimental parameters are important to perform vibrational studies with a suitable structure we compared our results with the structure experimental determined for DD2 by using X-ray diffraction (Karrouchi et al., 2023). Hence, optimized parameters for monomer of ABT in gas phase and water by using the same level of theory are compared in Table 3 with the corresponding to that benzotriazole derivative by using the root-mean-square deviation values (RMSD). The structures of those two compounds can be seen in Figure S5 and the benzotriazole moiety common is indicated in red circle. Very good correlations are found for bond lengths and angles, with values of 0.082 Å for bond lengths and between 1.3 and 2.3 ° for bond angles in both media, respectively. Here, clearly the bond angles values in solution are slightly higher than in the gas phase due to the hydration while some signs changes are observed in the dihedral $N4-N1-N3-N2$, $N4-N1-C5-C7$, $N4-N1-C5-C6$, $N3-N2-C6-C8$, $C5-C7-C9-H13$, $N2-C6-C8-C10$, $C7-C9-C10-H14$ and $C6-C8-C10-H14$ angles which were not considered in the RMSD values. These dihedral angles are indicated with the # symbol in Table 3. The very good agreements in these parameters and, obviously, between the structures indicate that the optimized ones can be used in the vibrational analyses.

Table 3. Comparison of Calculated Geometrical Parameters for the Monomer of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) Method with the Corresponding Experimental of C2 Conformer of 5-((1H-benzo[d][1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)methyl)Quinolin-8-ol (DD2)

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			Exp. ^b
Parameters	Gas Phase	Water	
Bond lengths (Å)			
N1-N3	1.366	1.354	1.351(5)
N1-C5	1.365	1.364	1.373(5)

N1-N4	1.388	1.391	1.442(5)
N3-N2	1.288	1.298	1.296(6)
N2-C6	1.381	1.378	1.378(6)
C5-C7	1.399	1.400	1.389(6)
C5-C6	1.405	1.404	1.377(6)
C7-H11	1.082	1.082	0.930
C7-C9	1.384	1.383	1.338(6)
C6-C8	1.402	1.404	1.411(7)
C9-H13	1.084	1.083	0.930
C9-C10	1.416	1.418	1.390(7)
C8-H12	1.083	1.083	0.930
C8-C10	1.382	1.382	1.382(8)
C10-H14	1.083	1.083	0.930
RMSD	0.082	0.082	
Bond angles (°)			
N3-N2-C6	108.6	108.4	109.9(3)
N3-N1-N4	122.7	123.0	120.5(3)
C5-N1-N4	126.6	126.4	129.5(3)
N1-N3-N2	108.9	109.0	109.6(4)
N3-N2-C6	108.6	108.4	107.2(4)
N1-C5-C7	134.1	133.8	133.3(4)
N1-C5-C6	103.2	103.5	103.4(3)
C7-C5-C6	122.5	122.5	123.3(4)
C5-C7-H11	121.5	121.8	122.2
C5-C7-C9	116.0	115.9	115.5(4)
H11-C7-C9	122.4	122.1	122.3
N2-C6-C5	108.6	108.3	109.9(4)
N2-C6-C8	130.7	130.8	130.7(4)
C5-C6-C8	120.6	110.7	119.5(4)
C7-C9-H13	119.1	119.1	117.7
C7-C9-C10	122.0	122.0	124.5(5)
C6-C8-H12	120.6	121.0	121.3
C6-C8-C10	117.2	117.0	117.5(5)
H12-C8-C10	122.1	121.9	121.2
C9-C10-C8	121.4	121.5	119.6(5)
C9-C10-H14	118.8	118.7	120.2
C8-C10-H14	119.7	119.6	120.2
RMSD	1.3	2.3	
Dihedral angles (°)			
C5-N1-N3-N2	0.0	0.0	1.3(5)
N4-N1-N3-N2#	-179.9	-179.9	178.9(4)
N3-N1-C5-C7	179.9	179.9	179.8(4)
N3-N1-C5-C6	-0.0	-0.0	-0.8(4)
N4-N1-C5-C7#	-0.0	-0.0	2.4(7)

N4-N1-C5-C6#	179.9	179.9	-178.2(4)
N1-N3-N2-C6	-0.0	-0.0	-1.1(5)
N3-N2-C6-C5	0.0	0.0	0.6(5)
N3-N2-C6-C8#	-179.9	-179.9	179.3(5)
N1-C5-C7-H11	0.0	-0.0	-0.3
N1-C5-C7-C9	180.0	179.9	179.7(4)
C5-C7-C9-H13	-179.9	-179.9	-179.6
C6-C5-C7-C9	0.0	0.0	0.4(6)
N1-C5-C6-N2	-0.0	-0.0	0.1(5)
N1-C5-C6-C8	-179.9	-179.9	-178.7(4)
C7-C5-C6-N2	179.9	179.9	179.6(4)
C7-C5-C6-C8	0.0	-0.0	0.8(7)
C5-C7-C9-H13#	-179.9	-179.9	179.3
C5-C7-C9-C10	0.0	-0.0	-0.7(7)
H11-C7-C9-H13	0.0	0.0	-0.6
H11-C7-C9-C10	180.0	179.9	179.3
N2-C6-C8-H12	0.0	0.0	-0.4
N2-C6-C8-C10#	-179.9	-179.9	179.7(5)
C5-C6-C8-H12	179.9	179.9	178.2
C5-C6-C8-C10	0.0	0.0	-1.8(7)
C7-C9-C10-C8	0.0	0.0	-0.4(8)
C7-C9-C10-H14#	-179.9	-179.9	179.6
H13-C9-C10-C8	179.9	179.9	179.6
H13-C9-C10-H14	0.0	0.0	-0.4
C6-C8-C10-C9	0.0	0.0	1.6(8)
C6-C8-C10-H14#	179.9	179.9	-178.4
H12-C8-C10-C9	-179.9	-179.9	-178.4
H12-C8-C10-H14	0.0	0.0	1.7
RMSD	0.9	0.9	

Note: #This work, Bold letter, RMSD values, #Indicate signs changes

NMR Study

Previously, we see the very good correlations in the geometrical parameters of monomer of ABT with the experimental structure reported for DD2. Now, we must see the correlations between the predicted NMR spectra of monomer and dimers of ABT in aqueous solution with the corresponding experimental

ones (Online Spectral Database, N/A). Therefore, in Tables 4 and 5 are summarized the comparisons of predicted ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR chemical shifts of those three species of ABT by using the GIAO and B3LYP/6-311++G** methods with the corresponding experimental obtained in CDCl_3 and Dimethyl sulfoxide- d_6 taken from Ref (Online Spectral Database, N/A).

Table 4. Observed and Calculated ¹H Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for Monomer of ABT in Aqueous Solution at B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	B3LYP/6-311++G**					Exp. ^b
	Monomer ^a	Dimer 1		Dimer 2		
11-H	7.73	11-H	8.11	11-H	8.25	7.50
12-H	8.17	12-H	8.07	12-H	8.10	7.90
13-H	7.55	13-H	8.02	13-H	7.99	7.40
14-H	7.45	14-H	7.58	14-H	7.49	7.25
15-H	4.97	15-H	5.04	15-H	5.00	5.9
16-H	4.97	16-H	5.04	16-H	5.05	5.9
		27-H	7.91	27-H	7.80	7.50
		28-H	8.27	28-H	8.25	7.90
		29-H	7.61	29-H	7.66	7.40
		30-H	7.43	30-H	7.52	7.25
		31-H	5.14	31-H	5.10	5.9
		32-H	5.13	32-H	5.08	5.9
RMSD	0.57		0.57		0.59	

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS, ^bOnline Spectral Database (N/A)

Table 5. Observed and Calculated ¹³C Chemical Shifts (δ in ppm) for Monomer of ABT in Aqueous Solution at B3LYP/6-311++G Level of Theory**

Atoms	B3LYP/6-311++G**				Experimental ^b
	Monomer ^a	Dimer 1		Dimer 2	
5-C	138.52	5-C	138.46	138.53	133
6-C	150.83	6-C	150.43	150.44	144
7-C	113.00	7-C	114.59	114.65	110
8-C	125.40	8-C	124.72	124.39	119
9-C	131.77	9-C	133.55	132.58	126
10-C	127.72	10-C	128.36	127.83	124
		21-C	137.63	138.43	133
		22-C	150.38	151.07	144
		23-C	113.57	113.92	110
		24-C	126.24	125.58	119
		25-C	132.20	132.32	126
		26-C	128.11	128.17	124
RMSD	5.39		5.65	5.60	

Note: ^aThis work GIAO/B3LYP/6-311++G** Ref. to TMS, ^bOnline Spectral Database (N/A)

The comparisons are evaluated by means of the RMSD values and presented in the same tables. Table 4 shows for the ¹H nucleus a RMSDs value of 0.57 ppm for the monomer and dimer 1 while

for dimer 2 the value is 0.59 ppm indicating that formation of dimeric species can also be seen in solution. For the ¹³C nucleus the value increase from 5.39 ppm for the monomer to 5.65 and

5.60 ppm. Note that despite of different experimental used solvents the better correlation is observed for the ^1H nucleus because the hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** method generate best results than the C atoms. Moreover, the few differences found for the three species could indicate the presence of dimeric species. Hence, the higher rmsds values observed could be associated to that the theoretical calculations were performed in different solvents and to the dimeric species formed. These reasonable correlations indicate that the structure of monomer and dimers are suitable to perform their vibrational studies.

Atomic Charges, Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) and Bond Orders

The presence of acceptors (N) and donor's (N-H) groups of H bonds in ABT are important not only to explain the properties and activities observed in this interesting benzotriazole derivative but also the mechanisms and sites of reaction. For these reasons, in this section the atomic MK and NPA charges, MEP and bond orders (BO) have been predicted and analysed. Hence, two different atomic charges were calculated only on the acceptors (N) and donor's (N-H) groups of H bonds in ABT in both environments, they are atomic MK and NPA charges (Glendening et al., 1996; Bredas, 2014). Thus, in Table S1 are presented the atomic charges, MEP and BOs on those N1, N2, N3, N4, H15 and H16 atoms of ABT involved in H bonds. Besides, Figure S6 shows the variations observed on calculated MK and NPA charges on N and H atoms corresponding to ABT in both media by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method. N1, N2 and N3 atoms belong to triazole moiety while N4 and H atoms to NH_2 groups. Hence, those three atoms are acceptors of H bonds while the other one's donors of H bonds. Regarding Figure S3 we observed that the MK charges on N1 in both media present positive values while the NPA corresponding to these atoms show negative values, as also are observed on N2 and N3. Both charges evidence the most negative values on N4, as expected because these atoms are linked to the most labile H15 and H16 atoms. This way, the two charges show positive values on those two H atoms.

If now from Table S1 are evaluated the MEP values computed from MK charges, it is observed higher values on the N atoms while the less negative MEP values are observed on H atoms due to these two atoms of NH_2 groups are most labile. Few variations on MEP values are observed when change the media from gas phase to the solution. However, when the mapped MEP surfaces of monomer in the two environments and of dimers in gas phase are shown in Figures S7 and S8 the energies values of monomer slightly increase from 0.0535 a.u in gas phase to 0.0543 a.u in solution while for both dimers the values decrease in solution. Hence, the nucleophilic sites of red colours are clearly observed on the N2 and N3 while the electrophilic sites with strong blue colours are observed on the two H atoms because these have less negative MEP values and are most labile. Analysing the mapped MEP surface for the dimers in gas phase it is observed from Figure S8 a slight higher energy for the dimer 2 (± 0.060 a.u.) than dimer 1 (± 0.0593 a.u.) and an, increases of blue coloration, but the red colour decrease, as a consequence of H bonds formation. The regions with green colours correspond to inert sites.

Evaluating the bond orders (BO) totals by atom, expressed as Wiberg bond index from Table S1, we can see that the N4 present lower values (2.824-2.821), as expected because these atoms are most labile and, for these reasons, they are less bonded to triazole rings while N1 have the higher values (3.610-3.617) because they are most bonded to triazole moieties. These studies support the existence of two clear nucleophilic and electrophilic regions in ABT associated to the acceptors and donor's groups de H bonds.

NBO and AIM Calculations

In the structure experimental reported for DD2 by using X-ray diffraction (Karrouchi et al., 2023) are observed C-H \cdots N bonds between two monomers in inverted positions. These interactions are also expected in dimers of ABT studies because these species containing donor and acceptor groups of H bonds, and, for these reasons, NBO and AIM calculations were performed for monomer and dimers with the

NBO 3.1 and AIM 2000 programs (Glendening et al., 1996; Bader, 1990; Biegler-König et al., 2001). In the NBO calculations, the donor-acceptor energy interactions were computed for the three species with the Second-Order Perturbation Theory Analysis of Fock Matrix in NBO Basis and by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. These main delocalizations energies for the monomer of ABT in both environments are shown in Table S2 while in Table S3 can be seen those predicted for both dimers. The results from Table S2 for the monomer show four different types of interactions which are: $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and, where $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ present the higher energy values in the two considered media. Evaluating the total energy value is clear that the monomer in solution has a slight higher stability with a value of 2110.95 kJ/mol while in gas phase the value is 1932.87 kJ/mol. When the calculated main delocalization energies for both dimers 1 and 2 of ABT in the two environments are analysed from Table S3, it is observed those same interactions but with higher energy values where, as in the monomer, the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ interactions present the higher energy values in the two considered media. Hence, both dimers are stable in gas phase because the total energy values are for dimers 1 and 2 are respectively 6110.91 and 6196.64 kJ/mol while in solution the values decrease respectively at 5115.69 and 5223.54 kJ/mol. In solution are observed H bonds elongations which decreases the stability of the corresponding monomers. Thus, the dimer 2 (6196.64 kJ/mol) is more stable than dimer 1 because it presents a slightly higher total energy value. The decreasing of energies for the dimers in solution could be attributed to higher solvation energy values (-96.11 kJ/mol), as compared with the monomer (-51.94 kJ/mol) (see Table 2). The values of both dimers are lower for the dimer 1 and, hence, the dimer 2 could be present in the solid phase, as observed in DD2 (Karrouchi et al., 2023).

Studying the H bonds interactions for monomer and dimers of ABT in the two environments through the topological properties with the AIM 2000 program the electron density, the Laplacian values and the $|\lambda_1|/\lambda_3$ ratio are calculated in the

bond critical points (BCPs) and in the ring critical points (RCPs) (Bader, 1990; Biegler-König et al., 2001). Thus, in Table S4 are presented those properties together with the distances of new H bonds for the dimers. The $|\lambda_1|/\lambda_3$ ratios are calculated with the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$). From these values it is possible to see that if the interaction is ionic or polar covalent interactions the ratio $\lambda_1/\lambda_3 < 1$ and $\nabla^2\rho(r) > 0$ (closed-shell interaction). Regarding the graphics obtained of the molecular model for the monomer of ABT in gas phase from Figure S9 it is observed the typical RCP1 and RCP2 due to the benzyl or phenyl (A1) and triazole (A2) rings. hence, there is not observed new H bonds interactions while when these graphics are obtained for the dimers in gas phase in Figures 3 and 4 two H bonds are shown.

Figure 3. Details of the Molecular Models for the Dimer 1 of ABT in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method Showing the Geometries of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs)**

For dimer 1, Figure 3 shows the formations of C7-H11...N19 and C8-H13...N18 interactions which generate a new RCP named RCPN. In the same way, for dimer 2 from Figure 4 are observed two C7-H11...N18 and C9-H13...N19 interactions. Moreover, the H bonds distances between those atoms for the two dimers increase in solution as a consequence of hydrations. Note that the atoms involved in the new interactions change due to the different positions of monomers in the respective dimers. Regarding Table S4 we observed that the

topological properties of dimer 2 present higher values than dimer 1 due to the lower distances between the H and N atoms. These NBO and AIM results show that dimer 2 present a slight higher stability in both media than dimer 1 and, for these reasons, this species will be present in the solid phase, as experimentally was observed for DD2 (Karrouchi et al., 2023).

Figure 4. Details of the Molecular Models for the Dimer 2 of ABT in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method Showing the Geometries of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs)**

Frontier Orbitals Studies

Frontier orbitals are appreciated factors to predict reactivities and behaviours of a species in diverse media calculating the gap values from the differences between the HOMO-LUMO and with which can be computed different descriptors (Parr & Pearson, 1983; Parr et al., 1999; Vakili et al., 2021; Brandán, 2021; Iramain et al., 2022). In this case, the behaviours of monomer and dimers of ABT were predicted in the two media together with the chemical potential (μ), electronegativity (χ), global hardness (η), global softness (S) and global electrophilicity index (ω) descriptors. Hence, in Table S5 are shown the results for monomer and dimers of ABT compared with the C2 conformer of DD2 (Karrouchi et al., 2023) and with antiviral agents such as, oseltamivir (Vakili et al., 2021), adamantadine (Brandán, 2021) and chloroquine (Romano et al., 2020) in aqueous solution at the same level of theory. Note that

the equations used are also presented in the table. Evaluating the gap values, we observed that the monomer in gas phase presents a lower gap value than the value in solution and, hence, it presents a higher reactivity in gas phase while the dimer 2 in both media are more reactive than dimer 1. Comparing these values with reported for the mentioned antiviral agents, the monomer is more reactive than oseltamivir (5.1892/5.1947 eV) while the dimer 2 of ABT evidence a higher reactivity than the monomer and oseltamivir, however, adamantadine (Brandán, 2021) and chloroquine (Romano et al., 2020) have lower values than ABT. Possibly, the presence of dimer 2 and of two N-NH₂ groups in ABT justify the biological activities observed for this species whose gap values are between 4.8817 and 4.5933 eV different from antiviral agents containing the C-NH₂ moiety, as amantadine whose gap values are around 4-3012-4.2994 eV. In reference to the descriptors, in the two dimers of ABT in both media are observed high (ω) values than the monomer while the antiviral amantadine presents the higher reactivity and the lower (ω) value. Hence, we not observed anything correlation between gap value and (ω), however, a lower global hardness (η) is related to lower reactivity or lower gap value.

The participations of all orbitals including of the benzotriazole rings in the HOMO-LUMO for monomer of ABT in both media is very clear, as observed in Figures S10 while for the dimers in both media from Figure S11 (only presented in gas phase because is the same in solution) shows that the participations of each monomer in the dimer are partial. Hence, changes in the HOMOs and LUMOs of each dimer are observed in Figure S11. These characteristics of HOMO-LUMO of both dimeric species could justify their biological properties as an inhibitor of cytochrome P450 enzymes.

Vibrational Study

B3LYP/6-311G* calculations optimized the monomer and the two dimers of ABT with C_1 symmetries. In the monomer with 16 atoms are expected 42 normal vibration modes while for the two dimers with 32 atoms are expected 90. The experimental ATR-IR spectrum of ABT in

the solid phase compared with the corresponding predicted for the three species in the gas phase are shown in Figure 5 while comparisons of Raman spectra are observed in Figure 6 (Online Spectral Database, N/A). The Raman spectra show better correlations with the experimental one due to the corrections from activities to intensities (Keresztury et al., 1993). The harmonic force fields were obtained using transferable scaling factors and normal internal coordinates and PED contributions $\geq 10\%$ in order to perform the complete assignments of three species of ABT (Pulay et al., 1983; Rauhut & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002).

Figure 5. Experimental Infrared Spectrum of 1 Amino-Benzotriazole (ABT) Compared with the Corresponding Predicted for Monomer and Dimers by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Figure 6. Experimental Raman Spectrum of 1 Amino-Benzotriazole (ABT) Compared with the Corresponding Predicted for Monomer and Dimers by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Thus, in Table 6 are summarized observed and calculated wavenumbers and assignments for monomer and dimers of ABT in the gas phase by using B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations. The positions and intensities predicted for both dimers are practically the same in the region of higher wavenumbers with some differences in the assignments in the 1700-40 cm^{-1} region related to NH_2 groups and to inter-monomers observed. Here, some discussions of assignments are presented for some groups by regions.

Table 6. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm^{-1}) and Assignments for Monomer and Dimers of ABT in Gas Phase by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Experimental ^a		B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a					
		MONOMER		DIMER 1		DIMER 2	
IR	Raman	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a	SQM ^b	Assignments ^a
		3413	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2$	3414	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2(\text{N}20)$	3414	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2(\text{N}20)$
3343w				3408	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2(\text{N}4)$	3412	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2(\text{N}4)$
		3338	$\nu_a\text{NH}_2$	3338	$\nu_s\text{NH}_2(\text{N}20)$	3338	$\nu_s\text{NH}_2(\text{N}20)$
3314w				3334	$\nu_s\text{NH}_2(\text{N}4)$	3337	$\nu_s\text{NH}_2(\text{N}4)$

3227w	3226w	3073	vC7-H11	3079	vC7-H11	3075	vC7-H11
3179w	3179w			3074	vC23-H27	3074	vC23-H27
3132w	3131w			3069	vC24-H28	3069	vC24-H28
3088sh	3069vs	3068	vC8-H12	3066	vC8-H12	3065	vC8-H12,vC10-H14
				3055	vC26-H30	3056	vC9-H13
		3053	vC10-H14	3055	vC9-H13	3054	vC26-H30
3020w				3042	vC25-H29	3041	vC25-H29
2988w	2996s	3040	vC9-H13	3041	vC10-H14	3040	vC10-H14
1667sh		1623	δNH_2	1622	$\delta\text{NH}_2(\text{N4})$	1622	$\delta\text{NH}_2(\text{N20})$
1643m				1622	$\delta\text{NH}_2(\text{N20})$, $\text{wagNH}_2(\text{N20})$	1622	$\delta\text{NH}_2(\text{N4})$, $\text{wagNH}_2(\text{N4})$
1608w	1594s	1594	vC5-C7	1594	vC21-C23	1593	vC21-C23
1608w	1594s			1592	vC5-C7	1592	vC5-C7
1608w	1594s			1568	vC5-C6,vC6-C8	1569	vC21-C22,vC22-C24
1502w	1504w	1568	vC5-C6,vC6-C8	1568	vC21-C22	1568	vC5-C6,vC6-C8
1476w		1478	vC8-C10	1479	vC24-C26	1479	vC24-C26
1456w	1451w			1478	vC8-C10	1477	vC8-C10,vN1-C5
		1433	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C7-}$	1433	$\beta\text{C24-H28},\beta\text{C23-H27}$	1433	$\beta\text{C24-H28},\beta\text{C23-H27}$
1419m	1424w			1431	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C7-H11}$	1431	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C7-H11}$
1408m	1394vs	1403	vN1-C5	1404	vN1-C5	1404	vN1-N4, $\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A2})$
1393w	1394vs			1403	vN17-C21	1403	vN17-
1372w	1377m	1364	vC9-C10,vC5-C6	1364	vC9-C10,vC8-C1	1364	vC25-C26,vC24-C26
1341w	1338w			1363	vC25-C26,vC24-C26	1363	vC9-C10,vC7-C9
1309w	1312sh	1301	ρNH_2	1302	$\rho\text{NH}_2(\text{N4})$	1303	$\rho\text{NH}_2(\text{N4})$
1296w	1298w			1301	$\rho\text{NH}_2(\text{N20})$	1299	$\rho\text{NH}_2(\text{N20})$
1274s		1295	vN2-N3	1293	vN2-N3	1293	vN2-N3
1246vs	1247vs			1292	vN18-N19	1292	vN18-N19
1233sh				1285	$\beta\text{C23-H27}$	1286	$\beta\text{C7-H11}$
		1284	$\beta\text{C7-H11}$	1285	$\beta\text{C7-H11},\beta\text{C8-H12}$	1285	$\beta\text{C23-H27}$
1228m	1225sh			1226	vN18-C22	1227	vN18-C22
1228m	1225sh	1225	vN2-C6	1225	vN2-C6	1225	vN2-C6
1172s	1172m			1157	$\beta\text{C9-H13},\beta\text{C7-}$	1155	$\beta\text{C9-H13}$
1144m	1146w	1152	$\beta\text{C9-H13},\beta\text{C7-}$	1154	$\beta\text{C25-H29},\beta\text{C23-C25}$	1153	$\beta\text{C25-H29},\beta\text{C23-C25}$
1118sh	1120m	1121	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C10-}$	1122	$\beta\text{C24-H28},\beta\text{C26-H30}$	1122	$\beta\text{C24-H28},\beta\text{C26-H30}$
1118sh	1120m			1118	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C10-H14}$	1118	$\beta\text{C8-H12},\beta\text{C10-H14}$
1106s				1102	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{C7-H11}$	1103	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{C5-C6}$
1098sh	1086vw	1099	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{C7-}$	1100	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A3}),\beta\text{C23-H27}$	1099	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A3}),\beta\text{C23-H27}$
1057m	1059vw			1048	vN17-N19	1047	vN17-N19
1040sh	999s	1039	vN1-N3	1041	vN1-N3	1042	vN1-N3
1000m	999s			1005	$\gamma\text{C9-H13}$	1000	$\gamma\text{C9-H13}$
957sh	955w			986	$\gamma\text{C25-H29},\gamma\text{C26-H30}$	985	$\gamma\text{C25-H29},\gamma\text{C26-H30}$
		984	$\gamma\text{C9-H13},\gamma\text{C10-}$	983	vC9-C10	984	vC9-C10
945m		983	vC9-C10	983	vC25-C26	983	vC25-C26
				956	$\gamma\text{C8-H12},\gamma\text{C10-H14}$	955	$\gamma\text{C10-H14},\gamma\text{C8-H12}$
934sh	924w	950	$\gamma\text{C8-H12}$	951	$\gamma\text{C24-H28}$	951	$\gamma\text{C24-H28}$
				930	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A3}), \beta\text{R}_2(\text{A4})$	930	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A3}),\beta\text{R}_2(\text{A4})$
903m		929	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{R}_2(\text{A2})$	929	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{R}_2(\text{A2})$	928	$\beta\text{R}_1(\text{A1}),\beta\text{R}_2(\text{A2})$

872m	873vw			862	γ C7-H11	864	γ C7-H11
848w	850vw	852	γ C7-H11	853	γ C23-H27	852	γ C23-H27
		834	wagNH ₂	839	wagNH ₂ (N4)	834	wagNH ₂ (N4)
783vs	790vs			834	wagNH ₂ (N20)	831	wagNH ₂ (N20)
783vs	790vs	771	wagNH ₂ , β R ₃ (A1)	771	wagNH ₂ (N4)	770	wagNH ₂ (N20)
770sh	770sh			771	ν C22-C24	769	wagNH ₂ (N4), β R ₃ (A1)
				766	γ C9-H13, γ C8-H12	765	γ C9-H13, γ C8-H12
753sh	751sh	756	γ C9-	758	τ R ₁ (A3), γ C25-H29	756	γ C25-H29, τ R ₁ (A3)
				744	τ R ₁ (A3)	745	τ R ₁ (A1), τ R ₁ (A2)
		740	τ R ₁ (A1), τ R ₁ (A2)	744	τ R ₁ (A1), τ R ₁ (A2)	740	τ R ₁ (A3), τ R ₁ (A4)
742vs	742s			726	ν N17-N20	726	ν N17-N20, ν N1-N4
727sh		724	ν N1-N4	726	ν N1-N4	725	ν N1-N4, ν N17-N20
659m	646w			639	τ R ₂ (A4), τ R ₁ (A4)	638	τ R ₂ (A4)
620w	625w	637	τ R ₂ (A2)	636	τ R ₂ (A2)	637	τ R ₂ (A2)
596m	602m			595	β R ₁ (A2)	595	β R ₁ (A4), β R ₁ (A2)
596m	602m	594	β R ₁ (A2)	594	β R ₁ (A4)	594	β R ₁ (A2), β R ₁ (A4)
568w	550sh			551	τ R ₂ (A1), τ R ₂ (A2)	552	τ R ₂ (A1), τ R ₂ (A2)
568w	550sh	550	τ R ₂ (A2), τ R ₂ (A1)	550	τ R ₂ (A3), τ R ₂ (A4)	550	τ R ₂ (A3), τ R ₂ (A4)
546sh				532	β R ₃ (A3)	532	β R ₃ (A3)
538m	537m	530	β R ₃ (A1)	531	β R ₃ (A1)	531	β R ₃ (A1)
505m	506w			497	β R ₂ (A3)	497	β R ₂ (A3)
489sh	476w	495	β R ₂ (A1)	495	β R ₂ (A1)	495	β R ₂ (A1)
431s	442w			427	τ R ₃ (A1), τ R ₂ (A1)	427	τ R ₃ (A1), τ R ₂ (A1)
417sh		424	τ R ₃ (A1), τ R ₂ (A1)	425	τ R ₃ (A3), τ R ₂ (A3)	425	τ R ₃ (A3), τ R ₂ (A3)
	281m	272	γ N1-N4, τ R ₂ (A2)	272	γ N17-N20, τ R ₂ (A4)	272	γ N1-N4, τ R ₂ (A2)
	281m			271	γ N1-N4, τ R ₂ (A2)	271	γ N17-N20, τ R ₂ (A4)
	242w			262	β N17-N20	261	β N17-N20
	242w	260	β N1-N4	261	β N1-N4	261	β N1-N4
	215sh			227	ButC21-C22	226	ButC21-C22
	215sh	223	ButC6-C5	225	ButC6-C5	223	ButC6-C5
	194sh	204	τ wNH ₂	211	τ wNH ₂ (N20)	206	τ wNH ₂ (N20)
	176m			205	τ wNH ₂ (N4)	196	τ wNH ₂ (N4)
		137	γ N1-N4	136	γ N17-N20	136	γ N1-N4
				134	γ N1-N4	135	γ N17-N
				43	γ _a N-H \cdots N	40	γ _a N-H \cdots N
				36	ν _a N-H \cdots N	34	ν _a N-H \cdots N
				20	δ N-H \cdots N	23	δ N-H \cdots N
				16	τ _w N-H \cdots N, τ _w N-	16	τ _w N-H \cdots N
				14	ν _s N-H \cdots N	15	ν _s N-H \cdots N
				12	τ _w N-H \cdots N, τ _w N-	9	τ _w N-H \cdots N

Abbreviations: ν , stretching; β , deformation in the plane; γ , deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ , torsion; ρ , rocking; τ w, twisting; δ , deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric; A1, A3, Benzyl; A2, A4; Triazole rings; ^aThis work, ^bFrom SQMFF/B3LYP/6-311++G** method.

Band Assignments. 4000-2000 cm⁻¹ region

In monomer and dimers, the NH₂ and C-H stretching (ν) modes are predicted practically in the same positions. The ν_a NH₂ modes are assigned to the IR band at 3343 cm⁻¹ while the symmetric mode at 3314 cm⁻¹, as reported for similar species (Karrouchi et al., 2023; Vakili et al., 2021; Brandán, 2021; Iramain et al., 2022). IR and Raman bands between 3227 and 2988 cm⁻¹ are related to ν C-H modes of three species of ABT because these modes in DD2 containing benzotriazole moiety were assigned to IR bands between 3100 and 2850 cm⁻¹ (Karrouchi et al., 2023).

Band Assignments. 1800-1000 cm⁻¹ region.

This region is typical of deformation (δ), wagging and rocking modes corresponding to NH₂ groups, in-plane or rocking (β) and out-of-plane (γ) deformations of CH and ν C=C, ν C=N, ν C-C modes (Karrouchi et al., 2023; Vakili et al., 2021; Brandán, 2021; Iramain et al., 2022). Hence, the shoulder and the IR band respectively at 1667 and 1643 cm⁻¹ are assigned to δ NH₂ modes of three species while the IR and Raman bands between 1608 and 1394 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν C=C and ν C=N modes with double or partial double bond character of three species while other ν C-C and ν C-N modes between 1377 and 1000 cm⁻¹ are assigned to those vibration modes of simple bonds. In DD2

(Karrouchi et al., 2023), the β CH modes are assigned between 1507 and 1100 cm⁻¹ while the γ CH deformations between 600 and 900 cm⁻¹. In the three species of ABT these modes are assigned between 1233 and 1120 900 cm⁻¹.

Band Assignments. 1000-10 cm⁻¹ region.

In this region are expected twisting and wagging modes of CH and NH₂ together with ν C-C modes and other skeletal modes, such as γ CH deformations and deformations and torsions of two rings. Thus, NH₂ wagging and twisting modes are predicted to 839/769 and 211/196 cm⁻¹, hence, these modes are assigned to the bands between 790/770 and 194/176 cm⁻¹, respectively. The remains skeletal and deformation (β_R) and torsion (τ_R) rings modes are assigned according to predicted by SQM calculations, as detailed in Table 6.

Force Constants

The application of the SQMFF approach and the Molvib program have permitted the calculations of scaled force constants for monomer and dimers of ABT in the two media (Pulay et al., 1983; Rauhut & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). These factors are presented in Table 7 compared with reported for the C2 conformer of DD2 in the same media (Karrouchi et al., 2023).

Table 7. Scaled Internal Force Constants for ABT in Gas Phase and Water Solution Compared with Reported for the C2 Conformer of 5-((1H-benzo[d][1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)methyl)quinolin-8-ol (DD2) in the Same Media by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G Method**

Force constant	B3LYP/6-311++G** method							
	Monomer		Dimer 1		Dimer 2		DD2 ^b	
	GAS	Water					GAS	Water
$f(\nu\text{NH}_2)$	6.31	6.30	6.32	6.30	6.33	6.32		
$f(\nu\text{C-H})_{A1,A3}$	5.14	5.15	5.14	5.16	5.16	5.16	5.09	5.14
$f(\nu\text{C-C})_{A1}$	6.28	6.28	6.28	6.29	6.29	6.29	6.27	6.28
$f(\nu\text{C-N})_{A2,A4}$	5.82	5.91	5.84	5.93	5.85	5.91	7.89	7.69
$f(\nu\text{N-N})_{A2,A4}$	5.79	5.73	5.80	5.74	5.80	5.74	5.98	5.96
$f(\delta\text{NH}_2)$	0.85	0.79	0.85	0.80	0.84	0.79		

Note: Units are mdyn Å⁻¹ for stretching and mdyn Å rad² for angle deformations. ^aThis work, ^bKarrouchi et al., 2023.

Here, it is necessary a clarification for those $f(\nu\text{N-N})_{A2,A4}$ and $f(\nu\text{C-H})_{A1,A3}$ force constants related to the benzotriazole rings (A1 and A3 correspond to benzyl ring while A2 and A4 to triazole ring). Hence, the $f(\nu\text{C-H})_{A1,A3}$ force constants related to the C-H bonds of benzyl rings have the same values in the three species of ABT and in the different media. Regarding the $f(\nu\text{NH}_2)$ force constants associated to NH_2 groups of monomer and dimers in both media it is observed that practically present the same values in gas phase and short changes undergoes in solution, as was also observed in the antiviral oseltamivir (6.42/6.32 mdyn \AA^{-1}), adamantadine (6.31/6.20 mdyn \AA^{-1}) and rimantadine (6.42 mdyn \AA^{-1}) (Vakili et al., 2021; Brandán, 2021; Iramain et al., 2022). Moreover, these same behaviours are observed in the $f(\nu\text{N-N})_{A2,A4}$ force constants associated to triazole rings of three species of ABT. These diminishing in the $f(\nu\text{NH}_2)$ and $f(\nu\text{N-N})_{A2,A4}$ force constants values indicate that these groups are hydrated in solution, as expected because NH_2 is a donor group of H bonds while the N atoms are acceptors of H bonds. For these reasons, in the DD2 species which contain a benzotriazole ring the same differences are observed (Karrouchi et al., 2023). Different behaviours in the $f(\nu\text{C-N})_{A2,A4}$ force constants values of monomer and dimers are observed because their values increase in solution but the values practically are similar in the three species. These studies support the presence of the three species of ABT in the two media.

Electronic Spectra

The predicted electronic spectrum of monomer and dimers of ABT in aqueous solution by using the B3LYP/6-311++G** method are compared in Figure S12 with the experimental of 1,2,3-Benzotriazole in aqueous solution taken between 200 and 350 nm (Breuer et al., 2012). Two bands with different intensities can be observed in the experimental spectrum where the most intense is located at c.a. 210 nm and other less intense at 277 nm. In the monomer,

two intense bands at 190 and 240 nm with a shoulder at 260 nm are observed but in the dimers the intense band is at 240 nm and the shoulder at 260 nm and the other band of lower λ it is not observed in these species. The bands observed are associated to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$, $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions predicted for these species by NBO calculations. Note that the band intense at 190 nm in the monomer is not predicted in the dimers. The experimental UV spectrum of 1,2,3-benzotriazole show the presence clear of monomer and dimers of this benzotriazole derivative and, hence, both bands should be observed in ABT and, as a consequence the three species of ABT are present in the experimental ^1H - and ^{13}C -NMR, IR and Raman spectra.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were obtained of this investigation:

Structural, topological and vibrational properties of monomer and two dimers (1 and 2) of 1-Aminobenzotriazole (ABT) have been studied combining hybrid B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations with the experimental ^1H -, ^{13}C -NMR, FT-IR and FT-Raman spectra.

B3LYP/6-311++G** calculations predict C-H \cdots N interactions of dimeric species, as was experimentally observed in benzotriazole derivatives.

NBO and AIM calculations suggest that dimer2 with inverted positions of its monomers could be present in the solid phase because it evidence higher stabilities in both media.

Frontier orbitals studies support a higher reactivity of dimer 2 of ABT than the monomer and dimer 1. This way, the presence of dimer 2 containing N- NH_2 groups in ABT could justify the biological activities observed for this species with gap values between 4.5933 and 4.8164 eV different from antiviral agents containing the C- NH_2 moiety, as amantadine and chloroquine whose gap values are around 4.3012-4.1116 eV.

The presence of bands of monomer and of both dimers are predicted in the vibrational spectra and, hence, its complete assignments of monomer and dimers have been performed. The scaled force constants are also reported for the three studied species.

The presence of monomer and dimer species of ABT are predicted by using their UV spectra, as was experimentally observed in benzotriazole derivatives.

Supplementary Information

Figures S1-S12 (Appendix 1) and Tables S1-S5 (Appendix 2).

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Author Contribution

ME. Manzur and PG. Cataldo performed the calculations MA. Iramain and MV. Castillo: prepared figures and tables. SA. Brandán: wrote the main manuscript text. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Figure S1. Orientations, Magnitudes and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors of Monomer of ABT:(a) in Gas Phase (Upper) and (b) in Aqueous Solution (Bottom) by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure S2. Orientations, Magnitudes and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors of Dimer 1 of ABT:(a) in Gas Phase (Upper) and (b) in Aqueous Solution (Bottom) by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure S3. Orientations, Magnitudes and Directions of Dipole Moment Vectors of Dimer 2 of ABT:(a) in Gas Phase (Upper) and (b) in Aqueous Solution (Bottom) by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure S4. Optimized Structures of Antiviral Amantadine, Oseltamivir and Rimantadine Agents in Gas Phase with the Atoms Labelling by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) Method. In Red Circle are Observed the Common C-NH₂ Group

Figure S5. Optimized Structure of ABT in Gas Phase with the Atoms Labelling by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) Method Compared with the Corresponding Experimental for the C2 Conformer of 5-((1H-benzo[d][1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)methyl)quinolin-8-ol (DD2)

Figure S6: Variations Observed on Calculated MK and NPA Charges on N and H Atoms Corresponding to ABT in Both Media by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method. The N Atoms Belong to Triazole Moiety while the H Atoms to NH₂ Groups

Figure S7. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surface on the Molecular Surfaces of Monomer of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method. Isodensity Value of 0.005

Figure S8. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surface on the Molecular Surfaces of Dimer 1 (Upper) and Dimer 2 (Bottom) of ABT in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method. Isodensity Value of 0.005

Figure S9. Details of the Molecular Models for the Monomer of ABT in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method Showing the Geometries of All Their Ring Critical Points (RCPs).

Figure S10. Comparisons Between the Frontier Orbitals HOMO-LUMO of Monomer of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure S11. Comparisons Between the Frontier Orbitals HOMO-LUMO of Dimers 1 (Left) and 2 (right) of ABT in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Figure S12. Experimental Electronic Spectrum of 1,2,3-Benzotriazole in Ethanol Solvent Compared with the Corresponding Predicted for Monomer and Dimer of ABT in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-311++G** Method

Appendix 2

Table S1. Merz-Kollman and NPA Charges (a.u.), Molecular Electrostatic Potentials (MEP) (a.u.) and Bond Orders, Expressed as Wiberg Indexes for ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Atoms	GAS PHASE				AQUEOUS SOLUTION			
	MK	NPA	MEP	BO	MK	NPA	MEP	BO
N1	0.512	-0.081	-18.278	3.610	0.523	-0.075	-18.276	3.617
N2	-0.328	-0.241	-18.377	3.106	-0.336	-0.245	-18.378	3.098
N3	-0.339	-0.054	-18.340	3.082	-0.345	-0.057	-18.341	3.081
N4	-0.903	-0.617	-18.337	2.824	-0.900	-0.617	-18.336	2.821
H15	0.392	0.366	-1.012	0.869	0.391	0.367	-1.011	0.869
H16	0.392	0.366	-1.012	0.869	0.391	0.367	-1.011	0.869

Table S2. Main Delocalization Energies (in kJ/mol) for Monomer of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Delocalization ^a	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a	
	Gas	Water
$\pi N2-N3 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	57.31	59.27
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* N2-N3$	117.54	119.55
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C7-C9$	66.63	66.59
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	73.94	72.23
$\pi C7-C9 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	84.27	82.81
$\pi C7-C9 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	69.01	68.97
$\pi C8-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	71.10	71.19
$\pi C8-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* C7-C9$	82.18	80.80
$\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	621.98	621.40
$LP(1)N1 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	150.02	150.06
$LP(1)N1 \rightarrow \pi^* N2-N3$	0.00	188.64
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$	150.02	338.71
$LP(1)N4 \rightarrow \sigma^* N1-N3$	46.36	45.19
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	46.36	45.19
$\pi^* N2-N3 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	171.05	164.69
$\pi^* C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	943.47	940.96
$\Delta E_{\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*}$	1114.51	1105.65
ΔE_{TOTAL}	1932.87	2110.95

^aThis work

Table S3. Main Delocalization Energies (in kJ/mol) for Dimers 1 and 2 of ABT in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

Delocalization ^a	B3LYP/6-311++G** Method ^a			
	DIMER 1		DIMER 2	
	Gas	Water	Gas	Water
$\pi N2-N3 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	56.64	58.56	56.93	58.77
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* N2-N3$	120.22	120.55	119.80	120.34
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C7-C9$	64.16	65.33	64.92	65.71
$\pi C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	73.36	71.94	73.82	72.36
$\pi C7-C9 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	88.07	84.90	86.74	84.27
$\pi C7-C9 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	71.06	70.10	72.40	70.93
$\pi C8-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	71.14	71.31	70.77	70.93
$\pi C8-C10 \rightarrow \pi^* C7-C9$	80.30	80.01	79.29	79.25
$\pi N18-N19 \rightarrow \pi^* C21-C22$	56.85	58.81	56.85	58.94
$\pi C21-C22 \rightarrow \pi^* N18-N19$	119.67	120.18	119.80	120.09
$\pi C21-C22 \rightarrow \pi^* C23-C25$	59.57	66.25	59.73	66.21
$\pi C21-C22 \rightarrow \pi^* C24-C26$	72.82	71.94	72.94	72.02
$\pi C23-C25 \rightarrow \pi^* C21-C22$	84.90	83.18	84.77	83.14
$\pi C23-C25 \rightarrow \pi^* C24-C26$	69.22	69.05	69.26	69.14
$\pi C24-C26 \rightarrow \pi^* C21-C22$	71.48	71.35	71.52	71.35
$\pi C24-C26 \rightarrow \pi^* C23-C25$	73.53	80.80	73.32	80.72
$\Delta E_{\pi \rightarrow \pi^*}$	1232.97	1244.26	1232.85	1244.18
$\sigma N17-N20 \rightarrow \sigma^* C26-H30$	121.39	0.00	121.43	0.00
$\sigma N20-H31 \rightarrow \sigma^* C25-H29$	0.00	0.00	43.56	0.00
$\sigma N20-H31 \rightarrow \sigma^* C26-H30$	284.37	0.00	284.20	0.00
$\sigma N20-H32 \rightarrow \sigma^* C25-C26$	47.23	0.00	0.00	0.00
$\sigma N20-H32 \rightarrow \sigma^* C26-H30$	397.56	0.00	400.07	0.00
$\Delta E_{\sigma \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	850.55	0.00	849.25	0.00
$LP(1)N1 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	147.55	149.14	148.10	149.56
$LP(1)N1 \rightarrow \pi^* N2-N3$	178.03	188.60	179.32	189.35
$LP(1)N17 \rightarrow \pi^* N18-N19$	0.00	189.19	0.00	189.77
$LP(1)N17 \rightarrow \pi^* C21-C22$		150.02		
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$	325.58	676.95	327.42	528.69
$LP(1)N4 \rightarrow \sigma^* N1-N3$	45.48	45.14	45.94	45.31
$LP(1)N20 \rightarrow \sigma^* N17-N19$	46.52	45.35	46.40	45.39
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	92.00	90.50	92.34	90.71
$\pi^* N2-N3 \rightarrow \pi^* C5-C6$	166.78	0.00	166.49	162.02
$\pi^* C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C7-C9$	879.14	1125.26	919.64	1138.13
$\pi^* C5-C6 \rightarrow \pi^* C8-C10$	894.69	912.37	996.18	989.11
$\pi^* N18-N19 \rightarrow \pi^* C21-C22$	164.27	162.23	163.02	162.14
$\pi^* C21-C22 \rightarrow \pi^* C23-C25$	312.58	0.00	292.35	0.00
$\pi^* C21-C22 \rightarrow \pi^* C24-C26$	836.50	904.13	861.12	908.56
$\pi^* C24-C26 \rightarrow \pi^* C23-C25$	355.84	0.00	295.99	0.00
$\Delta E_{\pi^* \rightarrow \pi^*}$	3609.81	3103.98	3694.79	3359.97
ΔE_{TOTAL}	6110.91	5115.69	6196.64	5223.54

^aThis work

Table S4. Analysis of the Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Point (RCPs) for ATPO in Gas Phase and in Ethanol Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method							
MONOMER							
GAS PHASE							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2					
$\rho(r)$	0.0214	0.0543					
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1569	0.4332					
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1725	0.2503					
AQUEOUS SOLUTION							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2					
$\rho(r)$	0.0214	0.0546					
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1566	0.4344					
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1726	0.2527					
DIMER 1							
GAS PHASE							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2	RCP3	RCP4	RCPN	H11...N19	H13...N18
$\rho(r)$	0.0215	0.0542	0.0215	0.0544	0.0023	0.0052	0.0058
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1568	0.4324	0.1569	0.4332	0.0120	0.0158	0.0169
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1738	0.2502	0.1734	0.2511	0.1444	0.1803	0.1883
Distances						2.812	2.765
AQUEOUS SOLUTION							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2	RCP3	RCP4	RCPN	H11...N19	H13...N18
$\rho(r)$	0.0214	0.0545	0.0214	0.0546	0.0002	0.0006	0.0003
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1568	0.4344	0.1566	0.4344	0.0001	0.0003	0.0001
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1727	0.2527	0.1729	0.2526	0.0947	0.1243	0.1176
Distances						3.806	4.126
DIMER 2							
GAS PHASE							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2	RCP3	RCP4	RCPN	H11...N18	H13...N19
$\rho(r)$	0.0215	0.0542	0.0215	0.0544	0.0022	0.0068	0.0042
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1568	0.4325	0.1568	0.4332	0.0108	0.0198	0.0129
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1736	0.2496	0.1736	0.2510	0.1460	0.1899	0.1718
Distances						2.699	2.899
AQUEOUS SOLUTION							
Parameter#	RCP1	RCP2	RCP3	RCP4	RCPN	H11...N18	H13...N19
$\rho(r)$	0.0214	0.0545	0.0214	0.0546	0.0003	0.0007	0.0005
$\nabla^2\rho(r)$	0.1567	0.4344	0.1566	0.4344	0.0002	0.0003	0.0002
$ \lambda_1 / \lambda_3 $	0.1729	0.2525	0.1728	0.2525	0.1000	0.1286	0.1143
Distances						3.752	3.881

Note: #Parameters in a.u., Distances in Å

Table S5. Frontier Molecular Orbitals, HOMO and LUMO, Gap Values and Chemical Potential (μ), Electronegativity (χ), Global Hardness (η), Global Softness (S) and Global Electrophilicity Index (ω) Descriptors for Monomer and Dimers of ABT in Gas Phase and Water Solution by Using B3LYP/6-311++G Calculations**

B3LYP/6-311++G** Method							
Orbital	MONOMER		DIMER 1		DIMER 2		
	Gas	Water	Gas	Water	Gas	Water	
HOMO	-6.8137	-6.8246	-6.4573	-6.6260	-6.4246	-6.5688	
LUMO	-1.6245	-1.6300	-1.8286	-1.7443	-1.8313	-1.7524	
GAP	5.1892	5.1947	4.6287	4.8817	4.5933	4.8164	
DESCRIPTORS (eV)							
χ	4.2191	4.2273	4.1430	4.1852	4.1280	4.1606	
μ	-4.2191	-4.2273	-4.1430	-4.1852	-4.1280	-4.1606	
η	2.5946	2.5973	2.3144	2.4409	2.2967	2.4082	
S	0.1927	0.1925	0.2160	0.2048	0.2177	0.2076	
ω	3.4304	3.4401	3.7082	3.5880	3.7097	3.5941	
Orbital	DD2 ^b		Adamantadine ^c	Chloroquine ^d		Oseltamivir ^e	
	Gas	Water	Water	S(-) Form	R(+) Form		
HOMO	-6.3457	-6.3892	-6.4736	-6.0055	-5.9865	-6.7375	-6.9906
LUMO	-2.1279	-2.1633	-0.4218	-1.7061	-1.6844	-1.4558	-1.6245
GAP	4.2178	4.2259	4.1116	4.2994	4.3021	5.2817	5.3661
DESCRIPTORS (eV)							
χ	-2.1089	-2.1130	-2.0558	-2.1497	-2.1511	-2.6409	-2.6830
μ	-4.2368	-4.2763	-3.3130	-3.8558	-3.8354	-4.0967	-4.3075
η	2.1089	2.1130	2.0558	2.1497	2.1511	2.6409	2.6830
S	0.2371	0.2366	0.2432	1.0748	1.0755	1.3204	1.3415
ω	4.2559	4.3272	2.6695	3.4581	3.4194	3.1775	3.4578

Note: ^aThis work, ^bKarrouchi et al., 2023 for the C2 conformer of 5-((1*H*-benzo[d][1,2,3]triazol-1-yl)methyl)quinolin-8-ol (DD2) (Karrouchi et al., 2023), ^c Brandán, (2021), ^d Romano et al., (2020), ^eVakili et al., (2021).

Note: $\chi = - [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\mu = [E(\text{LUMO}) + E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $\eta = [E(\text{LUMO}) - E(\text{HOMO})]/2$; $S = 1/2\eta$; $\omega = \mu^2/2\eta$